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The Significance of Ichnofabric Analysis for Sedimentological Interpretation: an outcrop study at Palaran, Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Ichnofabric analysis by optimizing ichnological data such as: ichnotaxa, tiering styles, BI (bioturbation index), diversity, burrow diameter, and penetration depth have been done at Palaran outcrop in Samarinda Area, Kutai Basin Indonesia. The overall sedimentological interpretation is impressive that the substrate consistency, substrate stability, erosional and burial processes, and tranquil event had been determined. However, those interpretations are sedimentological events that should not be connote to the specific depositional environment.

Keywords: ichnofabric, tiering, ichnotaxa, diversity, burrow diameter, penetration depth, substrate consistency, substrate stability, erosional, burial, tranquil.

INTRODUCTION

Ichnofabric is sediment fabric that had been modified by interaction of tracemaker with sediment (modified from Ekdale, et al. 1984; Bromley, 1996; Taylor, et al. 2003). The styles of interaction are printed in sediment as biogenic sedimentary structures or ichnofossil that can be applied to understand sedimentological processes by detailed ichnological analysis (after Goldring, 1964; Howard, 1975).

Previous ichnological study in Samarinda Area had been organized by Arifullah (2005) who emphasized on ichnofacies modelling of distinct deltaic depositional environment. Continuous ichnological research based on ichnofabric criteria has been carried out to determine sedimentological processes in 400's meters of outcrops in the Samarinda Area, East Kalimantan. However,

Figure 1 The location map of Palaran outcrop in Samarinda Area (From Google Earth 2016).

PROCEEDINGS

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only Palaran sandstone outcrop will be displayed in this paper.

Palaran sandstone is located at the side of roadcut to the Palaran Stadium of Samarinda City (Figure 1). The 10's meters of height and 16's meter of length of this outcrop was scrutinised. Lithologically, this outcrop is dominated by sandstone, interbedding sandstone and shale and capped by coal. According to GRDC's geo-

logical map (Supriatna et al, 1995) this outcrop corresponds to Balikpapan Formation and deposited at Early Miocene epoch (Bachtiar, 2004) and interpreted as deltaic origin (Allen and Chambers, 1998; Bachtiar, 2004). This paper is not intended to prove neither it is deltaic deposit or not, but to demonstrate the significance of ichnofabric analysis for sedimentological analysis.

Table 1: Ichnofabric in Palaran outcrop, some ichnofossil displayed in figure 2.

Code	Ichnofossil	BI	Div	D _{min}	D _{max}	PD
Ch-1	<i>Chondrites, Scolicia, Diplocraterion, Ophiomorpha</i>	3	4	0.3	1	40
Ch-2	<i>Chondrites, Ophiomorpha</i>	2	2	0.3	3.8	40
Ch-3	<i>Chondrites, Scolicia</i>	3	2	0.3	0.5	75
Ch-4	<i>Chondrites</i>	1	1	0.5	0.8	45
mottled	unidentified	6	0	0	0	10
Op-1	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa</i> with fugichnia traces	1	1	2	3	13
Op-2	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa</i> with equilibrichnia traces	2-4	1	2	4	30
Op-3	<i>Ophiomorpha, Scolicia, Teichichnus, Rhizocorallium.</i>	3	4	2	3	27
Op-4	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa, Thallasinoides, Rosselia</i>	1	3	1	4	15
Op-5	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa, Skolithos, Paleophycus</i>	2	3	1	1.5	10
Op-6	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa, Chondrites</i>	1	2	0.5	0.8	45
Op-7	<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa, Siponichnus</i>	3	2	1	1.5	30
Op-8	<i>Ophiomorpha.</i>	1	1	0.5	0.8	45
Pa-1	<i>Paleophycus.</i>	2	1	0,8	1	5
Pa-2	<i>Paleophycus, Rhizocorallium, Teichichnus, Planolites, Asterosoma</i>	3	5	1	1.7	15
Pa-3	<i>Paleophycus, Ophiomorpha</i>	2	2	1	1.5	37
Pl-1	<i>Planolites</i>	4	1	0.3	0.5	5
Pl-2	<i>Planolites, Conichnus, Chondrites</i>	4	3	0.5	1	15
Sk-14	<i>Skolithos, Monocraterion</i>	2	2	0.5	0.7	30
Sk-1	<i>Skolithos, Bergauria</i>	1	2	1	2.2	5
Sk-2	<i>Skolithos, undertrack</i>	1-3	2	0.5	1	5-10
Rh-1	<i>Rhizocorallium, Teichichnus, Taenadium</i>	3	3	1	1.5	15
Rh-2	<i>Rhizocorallium, Paleophycus, Teichichnus.</i>	3	3	1	2	25
Rh-3	<i>Rhizocorallium, Ophiomorpha</i>	2	2	0.5	1	10
Th-1	<i>Thallasinoides, Skolithos, Asterosoma</i>	2	3	1	2	12
ut	undertrack, <i>Planolites</i>	1	0	0	0	0.5
Zo-1	<i>Zoophycus.</i>	3	2	1.5	2	38

Figure 2 The some ichnofossil in Palaran outcrop. A. *Ophiomorpha* (Op), B. *Siphonichnus* (Si), C. *Zoophycos* (Zo), D. *Thalassionides* (Th) and *Asterosoma* (As), E. *Thalassionides* (Th), *Teichichnus* (Te), *Planolites* (Pl), F. *Scolicia* (Sc).

PROCEEDINGS

GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

DATA AND METHODS

Giving substance to ichnofabric as a significant tool for sedimentological analysis, therefore ichnological data such as: ichnotaxa, tiering styles, BI (bioturbation index), diversity, burrow diameter, and penetration depth are accentuated. The ichnofabric criteria are displayed in table 1 and visualize on single sedimentary log (figure 3).

The determination of BI (bioturbation index) value refers to Bottjer and Drosser (1986). The usage of BI for inference of mobility tracemaker (Rhoads, 1975). The quantification of diversity is based on amount of variability of trace fossil presented on each tier neither similar ethology or not. Dmin and Dmax show minimum and maximum diameter of burrow that personified tracemaker size. PD (penetration depth) visualize the capability of tracemaker burrowing. However, the inspiration from Bambach (1983) and Ekdale and Bromley (1991), we suggest that the tiering styles are fundamental data that should be resolved as first priority.

Furthermore, the method of ichnofabric grouping that proposed does not follow the concepts of ichnofossil assemblage, ichnocoenosis (Dorjes and Hertweck, 1975), suite (Bromley, 1975) or ichnofacies (Seilacher, 1967), but adopting the idea of the exploitation of eco-space and similar strategy of tracemaker to exploit environmental resources (Bambach, 1983) that had been employed by Ekdale and Bromley (1991) previously.

Ichnofossil commonly receive a paleontologic or zoologic connotation despite prefix ichno- that are defined as artifact of organism's activity clearly. It is important to stress that ichnofossil is biogenic sedimentary structure, consequently it should be receiving equal that devoted to structures developed by physical processes. However, the terminology of primary or secondary should be implied in cronologic order of development (Pettijohn and Potter, 1964). If ichnofossil is formed at the time of deposition or shortly thereafter and before consolidation of the rock in which they are found, thus ichnofossil is primary sedimentary structures.

The next paragraphs will elucidate the general sedimentological significance of ichnofabrics and the one's summarize at table 2.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 summarizes the significance of ichnofabric associations that respect to tiering styles, BI (bioturbation index), diversity, burrow diameter, penetration depth and ethology can be applied in sedimentological interpretation. The sedimentological parameters such as: substrate consistency, substrate stability, erosional and burial, tranquil event, etc, will be outlined by its ichnofabric characteristics.

Substrate consistency

The tracemaker colonized the substrate shortly thereafter and before the consolidation. Bromley (1996) suggested that substrate consistency such as thixotrophy or dilatancy can be inferred from the ichnofossil burrow wall and lining that developed by tracemaker for reinforcement their domicile from collapse. The thick burrow wall and lining or constructed of pelleted wall (e.g., *Ophiomorpha*) is an example of tracemaker that adapts to thixotrophic substrate. While *Thalassinoides* or *Chondrites* that has no wall or no lining indicates the tracemaker create the trace in the dilatancy substrate. Furthermore, level substrate stability can be elucidated by ichnofabric analysis based on the tiering level (e.g., Pa 3 - Ch 4 ichnofabric association). The occurrence together of *Ophiomorpha* (domichnia-suspension feeding), *Teichichnus*, *Rhizocorallium*, and *Scolica* (all of them are fodonichnia-deposit feeding) on the deepest tier of Pa 1 - Op 3 ichnofabric association maybe can be interpreted that the substrate stability is variable. The other interpretation by biological means may be can depict as community replacement as respond to the overall change of substrate stability. Overall of the change of sediment stability depict by line graphic in figure 3. However the change of substrate stability has critical value of inteprete further of sedimentological process in the sediment water interface.

Substrate stability

Deduction model from Seilacher (1967) and extended by Gingras, et al (2007) has describe the relationship

PROCEEDINGS

GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

Table 2. Ichnofabric association and its interpretation #Palaran sandstone outcrop

Ichnofabric Association	Interpretation	
	Code	Sedimentological event
Op 7 - Ch 3	1	1. Thixotropic substrate of highest tier and dilatancy substrate of deeper ones. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport on substrate water interface. 3. The substrate of highest tier was eroded and buried.
Pa 3 - Ch 4	2	1. Thixotropic level of substrate increase upward. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport on substrate water interface. 3. The substrate of highest tier was eroded and buried.
Op 8	3	1. Thixotropic substrate . 2. Bedload and suspended load transport. 3. The substrate was eroded and buried.
Pa 2 - Ch 2	4	1. The change of thixotropic to dilatancy substrate. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport. 3. The substrate was eroded and buried. 4. Tranquil event
Op 5 - Ch 1	5	1. The change of thixotropic to dilatancy substrate. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport. 3. The substrate was eroded and buried.
mottled	6	1. Dilatancy substrate 2. The longer period of tranquil event.
Sk 2	7	1. Thixotropic substrate.
Pl 2	8	1. Tranquil event.
Op 4	9	1. The change of thixotropic substrate to dilatancy substrate. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport. 3. The substrate was eroded and buried. 4. Tranquil event
Sk 1	10	1. Thixotropic substrate.
Sk 14	11	1. Thixotropic substrate.
Pl 1 - Rh 3	12	1. Thixotropic level increase upward. 2. Tranquil event. 3. Oxygen content increase upward.
ut	13	1. Dilatancy substrate.
Th 1 - Rh 2 - Zo 1	14	1. Dilatancy substrate. 2. Oxygen content increase upward. 3. Tranquil event
Pa 1 - Op 3	15	1. Dilatancy substrate in highest tier and dilatancy and thixotropic substrate in deeper tier. 2. Bedload and suspended load transport.
mottled - Rh 1 - Op 2	16	1. The change of thixotropic to dilatancy substrate. 2. The longer of tranquil event
Op 2	17	1. Thixotropic substrate. 2. Suspended load transport. 3. The substrate eroded and buried gradually and repeatedly.
Op 1	18	1. Thixotropic substrate. 2. Suspended load transport. 3. The substrate eroded and buried rapidly and repeatedly.

PROCEEDINGS

GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

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Figure 3 The sedimentary log of Palaran outcrop incorporates the criteria of lithofacies, paleocurrent and ichnofabric (ichnofossil content, tiering diagram, BI-bioturbation index, diversity, burrow diameter, penetration depth, ethology and the interpretations of oxygen content, substrate stability, and particulate organic mat-

PROCEEDINGS

GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

between distinctive ichnofossil with their exploitation methods for food (e.g., *Ophiomorpha* indicates permanent domicile that created by suspension feeder, or *Thalassinoides* indicates activity of deposit feeding). However, Ekdale et. al (1984) suggested the permanent domicile (domichnia) are not always hint at the artifact of suspension feeder, but can be produced of deposit feeder and even carnivore. Thus, domichnia ethology such as *Ophiomorpha*, *Skolithos*, *Paleophycus*, etc is not always associated with creation of suspension feeder that earn the food from suspended load transport.

Related to sediment transport, Middleton and Southard (1978) depicted the forces acting (drag force and lift force) during fluid flow on the sediment water interface. The resultant of those forces existence created grain movement as bedload and/or suspended load transport. Thus, we are discussing sediment stability practically.

If we pay attention on table 2, the development of *Ophiomorpha* of highest tier (beneath the sediment water interface) is reasonable to associate with bedload or suspended load transport. The construction of its burrow wall and lining support the substrate stability (c.f., Ekdale, et al, 1984). However, if only *Ophiomorpha* or associated with fugichnia or equilibrichnia developed in the substrate can be interpreted the condition of the sediment water interface is suspended load transport. More confident interpretation can be achieved if ichnometry data, such as, BI, burrow diameter or penetration depth are involved.

An additional point to keep in mind about substrate stability and consistency may vary vertically and laterally. The same sediment may show variability of stability and consistency according to the packing of grains, the grain size, water content and the mode of application of force (after Middleton and Southard, 1978; Bromley, 1996)

Erosional and burial intensities

The derivative of substrate consistency and stability interpretation is recognizing the other potential process such as erosional and burial on the sediment water interface. However other ichnotaxobases such as branching and burrow fill can help the interpretation. Accord-

ing to Howard (1978) studies, the deep penetration and branches of *Ophiomorpha* that form Y letter indicates the erosional and burial alternately and continuously (e.g., Op 7 - Ch 3; Op 2 ichnofabric association).

Diplocraterion (e.g., Goldring, 1964) and *Teichichnus* displays spreiten structures indicate erosional and burial process. Fortunately those ichnofossil associated with branched *Ophiomorpha* that explained in the preceding paragraph.

Tranquil event

Tranquil means free from disturbance such as erosional, burial or even predation. The interpretation of the tranquil event from ichnofabric association based on the intensity of detritus and deposit feeding ichnofossil of beneath sediment water interface (highest tier).

Pl 2, Pl 1 - Rh 3, Th 1 - Rh 2 - Zo 1 ichnofabrics indicates a tranquil event. It can be compared to Ekdale and Bromley (1991) that study deepwater deposit-pelagic environment. If related to substrate consistency, those ichnofabric associations developed on dilatancy substrate that may correspond to no deposition and no erosion event on the sediment water interface.

CONCLUSIONS

Ichnofabric analysis is a powerful tool to diagnose the detailed sedimentological factors in depositional environment. Chronologically, interpretation of Palaran outcrop indicates the alternation of substrate consistency, substrate stability, erosional and burial intensities, and tranquil event. An additional point to keep in mind, that sedimentological factors can take place in all possible depositional environment. However, the further interpretation can be achieved by the greater the degree of data integration, the more strong interpretation.

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PROCEEDINGS

GEOSEA XIV CONGRESS AND 45TH IAGI ANNUAL CONVENTION 2016 (GIC 2016)

Trans Luxury Hotel, Bandung, October 10 – 13, 2016

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